

Hg and MeHg speciation in the Scheldt Estuary and Belgian Part of the North Sea (BPNS) sediments

Tianhui Ma⁽¹⁾, Vincent Perrot⁽¹⁾, Martine Leermakers⁽¹⁾ and Yue Gao⁽¹⁾

(1)¹ Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Pleinlaan 2, Brussels, 1050, Belgium.

Mercury (Hg) is one of the most hazardous elements in both natural and urban environments, with monomethylmercury (MeHg) posing the greatest health risk due to bioaccumulation and biomagnification along the food chain. Coastal and estuarine zones are often the specific sites of high Hg contamination due to the anthropogenic activities. The BPNS (Belgian Part of the North Sea) has been subjected to long-term, recurring metallic pollution caused by atmospheric deposition, direct wastewater discharge from coastal industries, and input from the Scheldt Estuary, which is enriched in trace metals from its watershed, particularly the industrial site of Antwerp. Mercury and MeHg concentrations in sediment porewater are normally at ng/L level, and conventional methodology for sampling Hg and MeHg in porewater may not always produce accurate findings. The passive sampling technique of Diffusive Gradients in Thin-films (DGT) is a suitable technique preconcentrating labile Hg and MeHg. The labile fraction of Hg and MeHg measured by DGT is potentially bioavailable in aquatic systems. Both conventional porewater and DGT sampling were carried out in the Scheldt estuary and the BPNS during the two Belgica campaigns in March 2020 and March 2021. At sampling station S15 (upper Scheldt estuary and close to the industrial zone of Antwerp, salinity: 5 PSU), relatively high total Hg concentrations were found in both sediment porewater (10 to 90 ng/L) and solid phase (93 to 406 g/kg). The labile Hg concentrations in the porewater ranged from 2 to 35 ng/L at S15. However, at sample station SV (Close to Zeebrugge harbor in the BPNS, salinity: 29 PSU), lower total Hg concentrations were detected in sediment porewater (3 to 43 ng/L) and solid phase (31 to 147 g/kg). Labile Hg concentrations were fluctuated around 11 ng/L. The range of MeHg is from 0.5 to 3.6 ng/L at S15 and from 0 to 1.0 ng/L at SV.

Conference Topic:

Presentation preference: Oral

Corresponding Author: Tianhui Ma

e-mail address: tianhui.ma@vub.be